

Assessment of Salt Marsh Above-Ground Biomass Using UAV Multispectral Imagery and Open-Access Canopy Height Models

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Abstract: This study aims to identify and classify three dominant estuarine species (*Juncus maritimus*, *Phragmites australis*, and *Spartina patens*) in the Lima River estuary, Portugal, and develop species-specific AGB regression models utilising UAV multispectral imagery and drone-derived canopy height models (CHM). A Random Forest classifier mapped the landscape with a 91.9% overall accuracy. Utilising 75 destructive field samples, 504 predictive models combining vegetation indices and height variables were evaluated, revealing that model performance was heavily conditioned by species. *J. maritimus* yielded an additive-exponential model ($R^2 = 0.834$) driven by NDVI and CHM height. In contrast, models for *P. australis* ($R^2 = 0.498$) and the mat-forming *S. patens* ($R^2 = 0.453$) exhibited weaker fits and structural limitations resulting in extrapolation artefacts. Spatially extrapolating these models across 40.20 hectares demonstrated that while the UAV framework is highly reproducible, structurally complex species will necessitate higher-resolution 3-D structural metrics for accurate AGB prediction.

Keywords: blue carbon; salt marsh biomass; UAV-multispectral imaging; image classification; Iberian Peninsula.

1 Introduction

Salt marshes are highly productive coastal ecosystems providing key services including carbon sequestration, sediment trapping, and shoreline protection (McLeod et al. 2011). Accurate species-level above-ground biomass (AGB) estimation and mapping are fundamental to biomass monitoring, carbon stock assessment, and ecological management. UAV-based multispectral remote sensing combined with canopy height models (CHM) from Structure-from-Motion photogrammetry offers a fine-scale, repeatable approach to vegetation mapping in intertidal environments (Dandois and Ellis 2013, Westoby et al. 2012). However, spectral-structural regression model performance varies substantially between species with contrasting canopy architectures, and rigorous species-level classification is a prerequisite for spatially explicit AGB estimation. This study aims to (i) classify three ecologically dominant salt-marsh species in the Lima River estuary (Portugal) using a Random Forest (RF) classifier applied to UAV multispectral imagery and a drone-derived CHM, (ii) develop species-specific regression models for AGB prediction combining vegetation indices and canopy

height variables, and (iii) spatially extrapolate those models to produce per-pixel AGB maps.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area and field data

The study was conducted in the Lima River estuary near Viana do Castelo, northwestern Portugal (41.693° N, 8.790° W). Three riparian and salt-marsh species were selected based on ecological dominance and contrasting canopy forms (Figure 1): *Juncus maritimus* Lam. (JM), *Phragmites australis* (Cav.) Trin. ex Steud. (PA), and *Spartina patens* (Aiton) Muhl. (SP). Field campaigns were conducted in 3 of October 2024 just after peak AGB accumulation. A total of 75 destructive harvest samples (30 × 30 cm²) were collected (25 per species) with locations recorded using a Sfaira ONE GNSS RTK receiver (centimetre-level accuracy). Maximum canopy height was measured using the graduated (cm/mm) GNSS-receiver pole before cutting, samples were oven-dried at 60 °C to constant mass to obtain dry-weight AGB.

Figure 1. Different vegetation covers *Spartina patens* (a), *Juncus maritimus* (b) and *Phragmites australis* (c).

2.2 UAV image acquisition and processing

Aerial imagery was acquired using a DJI Mavic 3 Multispectral UAV (20 MP RGB, 5 MP multispectral with G: 560 nm, R: 650 nm, RE: 730 nm, NIR: 860 nm). Flights were conducted immediately prior to sample collection with a flight altitude of 60 m, starting one hour before low tide, resulting in a GSD of approx. 1.6 cm (RGB) and ~3.125 cm (multispectral), with 80%/70% frontal/lateral overlap. Processing in Agisoft Metashape (v2.3.0) produced a calibrated multispectral orthomosaic (3.125 cm GSD) and a DSM (10 cm GSD). A CHM was derived by subtracting a LiDAR-based DTM from the DSM. The DTM was obtained from DGT (Direção-Geral do Território) at 50 cm GSD and resampled to 10 cm using bilinear interpolation.

2.3 Classification, vegetation indices and regression modelling

A RF pixel-based classifier (Breiman 2001) was trained on the multispectral orthomosaic and CHM to map six land

cover classes (JM, PA, SP, Bare Soil, Closed Water, Open Water), with 48 training samples (4 for each class) of approximately 10m² each, selected by manual photointerpretation of the higher-resolution RGB orthomosaic. Twelve vegetation indices (VIs) were computed at 3.125 cm resolution (Table 1). Classification accuracy was assessed following Olofsson et al. (2013, 2014) via stratified random sampling (AcATaMa/QGIS), reporting area-adjusted overall accuracy, user's and producer's accuracy.

For each 30 × 30 cm² sampling area, spectral and CHM predictor values were extracted using area-weighted means. Seven regression equation types (Table 2) were fitted for each combination of VI, height variable (CHM-derived or *in situ*), and AGB per species, yielding 504 fitted models (7 forms × 12 VIs × 2 height variables × 3 species).

For equations 6 and 7, a two-stage grid search was applied to identify optimal nonlinear parameters: a coarse search over the range [-10, 10] at step 0.1.

Model performance was evaluated using R², adjusted R², RMSE, nRMSE, MAE, bias, p-value, and VIF. Best-performing species-specific models were spatially applied to generate per-pixel AGB maps at 3.125 cm resolution.

3 Results

3.1 Classification accuracy

Stratified random sampling allocated 1,927 reference points across the six classes proportionally to the mapped area, where 1,873 points were successfully labelled through visual interpretation of the RGB orthomosaic (Table 3), constituting the final reference dataset.

Table 1. Vegetation indices computed from the multispectral orthomosaic.

Index	Abbreviation	Formula
Chlorophyll Vegetation Index	CVI	$(\text{NIR} \times \text{Red}) / \text{Green}^2$
Difference Vegetation Index	DVI	$\text{NIR} - \text{Red}$
Enhanced NDVI	ENDVI	$((\text{NIR} - \text{Green}) - 2 \cdot \text{Red}) / ((\text{NIR} - \text{Green}) + 2 \cdot \text{Red})$
Excess Red Index	ExR	$1.4 \cdot \text{Red} - \text{Green}$
Green Chlorophyll Index	GCI	$(\text{NIR} / \text{Green}) - 1$
Green DVI	GDVI	$\text{NIR} - \text{Green}$
Green NDVI	GNDVI	$(\text{NIR} - \text{Green}) / (\text{NIR} + \text{Green})$
Modified Green Red Vegetation Index	MGRVI	$(\text{Green}^2 - \text{Red}^2) / (\text{Green}^2 + \text{Red}^2)$
Normalised Difference Red Edge Index	NDREI	$(\text{NIR} - \text{RedEdge}) / (\text{NIR} + \text{RedEdge})$
Normalised Difference Vegetation Index	NDVI	$(\text{NIR} - \text{Red}) / (\text{NIR} + \text{Red})$
Ratio Vegetation Index	RVI	Red / NIR
Renormalised DVI	RDVI	$(\text{NIR} - \text{Red}) / \sqrt{(\text{NIR} + \text{Red})}$

Table 2. Regression models equations.

#	Name	Formula
1	Linear	$\text{AGB} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{VI} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{H}$
2	Linear + interaction	$\text{AGB} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{VI} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{H} + \beta_3 \cdot (\text{VI} \times \text{H})$
3	Quadratic	$\text{AGB} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{VI} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{H} + \beta_3 \cdot \text{VI}^2 + \beta_4 \cdot \text{H}^2 + \beta_5 \cdot (\text{VI} \times \text{H})$
4	Log-linear	$\text{AGB} = \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{VI} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{H})$
5	Multiplicative power	$\text{AGB} = \beta_0 \cdot \text{VI}^{\beta_1} \cdot \text{H}^{\beta_2}$
6	Power-additive	$\text{AGB} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot (\text{VI})^p + \beta_2 \cdot (\text{H})^q$
7	Additive-exponential	$\text{AGB} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \exp(k_1 \cdot \text{VI}) + \beta_2 \cdot \exp(k_2 \cdot \text{H})$

The Random Forest classifier achieved an overall accuracy of 91.9% ± 0.6% (stratified area-weighted estimator, Olofsson et al. 2013), indicating strong agreement between the classified map and the reference data at the landscape scale. The full error matrix based on sample counts is presented in Table 4.

JM achieved the highest producer's accuracy but lower user's accuracy, reflecting commission errors from PA (4.2%) and SP (5.8%). PA showed the inverse pattern with 13.7% of true PA pixels being misclassified as JM, while the reverse confusion was negligible (<1%). SP was intermediate and exchanged pixels with JM more symmetrically, suggesting genuine spectral overlap rather than a one-way prior effect. The dominant confusion was a systematic bias toward JM, the largest class which absorbed misclassifications from every category except Open Water. Area-adjusted estimates differed notably from raw pixel counts (Table 5).

3.2 Model performance by species

Model performance varied substantially by species, with JM consistently producing the strongest fits, PA intermediate results, and SP the weakest. Within each equation type, the models were initially ranked internally according to their R² values.

For *Juncus maritimus*, an additive-exponential model using NDVI and CHM-derived height achieved R² = 0.834 (adj-R² = 0.819, nRMSE = 11.7%, R²_CV = 0.782, F = 55.14, p = 2.69 × 10⁻⁹, VIF = 1.006). NDVI (Tucker 1979) was the dominant predictor (p = 1.04 × 10⁻⁹), consistent with the species' homogeneous canopy.

Table 3. Stratified sample allocation and interpretation per class.

Class	Mapped area (m ²)	Area proportion	Samples allocated	Samples labelled
1 – Bare soil	21,322	0.047	90	90
2 – <i>Juncus maritimus</i> (JM)	216,715	0.473	912	882
3 – <i>Phragmites australis</i> (PA)	59,923	0.131	252	249
4 – <i>Spartina patens</i> (SP)	125,421	0.274	528	508
5 – Closed water	18,762	0.041	79	79
6 – Open water	15,644	0.034	66	65
Total	457,786	1.000	1,927	1,873

Table 4. Error matrix (sample counts). Rows = map classification, columns = reference data. Diagonal values indicate correct classifications. OA = Overall Accuracy.

	Bare	JM	PA	SP	Closed Water	Open Water	Total	User's acc.
Bare	90	0	0	0	0	0	90	1.000
JM	14	770	37	51	10	0	882	0.873
PA	0	6	236	7	0	0	249	0.948
SP	0	20	2	485	1	0	508	0.955
Closed W.	0	0	0	0	78	1	79	0.987
Open W.	0	0	0	0	2	63	65	0.969
Total	104	796	275	543	91	64	1,873	
Producer's acc.	0.861	0.967	0.856	0.894	0.853	0.985		OA = 0.919

Table 5. Per-class user's accuracy (acc.), producer's accuracy (with SD), and area-adjusted estimates with 95% confidence intervals.

Class	User's acc.	SD	Producer's acc.	SD	Mapped area (m ²)	Adjusted area (m ²)	95% CI (±m ²)
Bare soil	1.000	0.000	0.861	0.030	21,322	24,762	1,789
JM	0.873	0.011	0.967	0.006	216,715	195,578	5,343
PA	0.948	0.014	0.856	0.019	59,923	66,379	3,386
SP	0.955	0.009	0.894	0.012	125,421	133,958	4,223
Closed water	0.987	0.013	0.853	0.033	18,762	21,710	1,785
Open water	0.969	0.022	0.985	0.015	15,644	15,400	809

For *Phragmites australis*, a log-linear model using ExR and in situ height yielded $R^2 = 0.498$ (adj- $R^2 = 0.452$, nRMSE = 15.2%, $R^2_{CV} = 0.391$), with height as the primary driver ($p = 3.73 \times 10^{-4}$) and ExR marginally significant ($p = 0.101$). The cross-validation drop indicates limited generalisability beyond the training data.

For *Spartina patens*, an additive-exponential model using GDVI and CHM yielded the weakest fit ($R^2 = 0.453$, adj- $R^2 = 0.404$, nRMSE = 20.5%, $R^2_{CV} = 0.332$), reflecting the fundamental challenge of predicting AGB in this low-statured mat-forming grass from spectral and height variables alone.

3.3 VI and height variable contributions and AGB mapping

Across all species and equation types, approximately 51% of the top 10 ranked models included a statistically significant VI coefficient ($p < 0.05$), indicating that spectral information contributed meaningfully to approximately half of the assessed models. For the remaining models,

AGB variance was largely explained by height alone, with VI terms yielding non-significant coefficients.

Spatial extrapolation of the species-specific regression models across the classified extents yielded per-pixel AGB estimates covering 40.20 ha of the target vegetation. For JM (21.67 ha), mean predicted AGB was 1888.88 g/m² with a SD of 639.11 g/m² and a median of 1723.32 g/m² (range: 667.05 – 7230.40 g/m²), with low spatial variance consistent with strong model performance. For PA (5.99 ha), mean predicted AGB was 1273.25 g/m² with a SD of 1624.50 g/m² and a median of 876.35 g/m² (range: 123.05 – 705,973.75 g/m²) an extreme predicted maximum was identified, indicative of log-linear instability at high ExR values. For SP (12.54 ha), mean AGB was 5303.18 g/m² with a SD of 4298.11 g/m² and a median of 3936.32 g/m² (range: 1338.80 - 215332.08), with high heterogeneity consistent with the weaker model fit.

4 Discussion

The RF classifier achieved OA = 91.9%, comparable to published values for UAV multispectral classification of salt-marsh vegetation (DiGiacomo et al. 2020, Norris et al. 2024, Routhier et al. 2023). The dominant source of classification error was a systematic directional bias toward JM, the largest class by mapped area (47.3% of the study extent). Commission errors from PA and SP into JM, combined with a JM omission of only 3.3%, resulted in an overestimation of the JM mapped area of approximately 10% relative to the area-adjusted estimate.

The most consequential accuracy limitation for the biomass modelling workflow was the PA omission rate of 14.4%, the highest among the three target species. The majority of omitted PA pixels were misclassified as JM, meaning that during AGB calculation with VI and CHM extraction, areas of true PA canopy were spatially processed under the JM mask. This misclassification of PA as JM should be considered alongside structural and ecological factors when interpreting those results.

Area-adjusted estimates, derived following Olofsson et al. (2014), differed substantially from raw mapped pixel counts for all three target species and might also be considered for assessed biomass totals or carbon stock estimates at the landscape scale.

Species-specific model performance reflected contrasting canopy architectures. The strong JM result ($R^2 = 0.834$) is consistent with its homogeneous forming canopy: NDVI and CHM height together provide a predictable spectral-structural signal. For PA, in situ height outperformed CHM, likely because the 10 cm CHM resolution cannot faithfully capture within-plot height variability of tall, dense *Phragmites* culms (2–3 m) at the $30 \times 30 \text{ cm}^2$ scale. It should be noted that, although the CHM is gridded at 10 cm, it derives from a 50 cm DTM, so its effective terrain resolution is coarser than the nominal grid suggests. Furthermore, the interpolation inherent to resampling tends to smooth microtopographic features such as slopes, potentially masking real ground elevation differences and introducing systematic errors in the derived canopy heights. The weak SP fit ($R^2 = 0.453$) reflects the intrinsic difficulty of predicting AGB in mat-forming grasses (canopy < 0.5 m) from height data alone, where biomass is more closely related to tiller density than to vertical structure.

Spatial extrapolation of AGB revealed distinct species-specific patterns and model behaviours across the study area. *Juncus maritimus* consistent with its homogeneous canopy and strong model performance. In contrast, *Phragmites australis* produced an ecologically implausible maximum ($705,973.75 \text{ g/m}^2$), identified as an extrapolation artefact arising from log-linear model instability. *Spartina patens* exhibited high spatial heterogeneity reflecting its complex mat-forming structure and a weaker model fit ($R^2 = 0.453$). These results suggest that while JM estimates are robust, PA and SP predictions should be treated as indicative rather than quantitatively precise due to model uncertainty and structural variability.

The sample size of $n = 25$ per species restricted the regression modelling, particularly for equations with three

or more parameters. Quadratic models (up to six parameters) left few residual degrees of freedom, increasing the risk of overfitting and producing inflated, non-generalizable R^2 values, this was evidenced by extreme VIF values ($> 3,000$) in PA models using GNDVI. Consequently, model selection prioritised adjusted R^2 and nRMSE, with VIF serving as a critical diagnostic filter. Additionally, while the $30 \times 30 \text{ cm}^2$ sampling unit effectively captured the fine-scale structures of JM and SP, it likely undersampled the patch-level biomass variability of PA. Future research might consider a larger number of sampling units and increased sample sizes (e.g., $50 \times 50 \text{ cm}^2$) to better capture structural variation in tall emergent species.

Finally, error propagation through the workflow combines uncertainties from classification, regression, and CHM. An exploratory estimate of the combined classification + regression contribution was computed as total AGB per species = mean AGB \times adjusted area, with error bounds given by RMSE \times adjusted area and further widened by the 95% CI of the classification accuracy (Table 5). This yields total biomass estimates of $369.4 \pm 78.6 \text{ t}$ for JM, $84.5 \pm 61.3 \text{ t}$ for PA, and $710.4 \pm 259.9 \text{ t}$ for SP, with the classification CI contributing an additional $\pm 2.2 \text{ t}$ (JM), $\pm 3.1 \text{ t}$ (PA), and $\pm 8.2 \text{ t}$ (SP). Although rough, this estimate captures the relative behaviour of the models: the resulting relative uncertainties — 21% (JM), 73% (PA), and 37% (SP) — track model performance directly, with PA dominated by regression error and further compounded by the log-linear extrapolation artefact reported earlier. The CHM inherits photogrammetric DSM errors and a scaling bias introduced when resampling the 50 cm DTM to 10 cm, which smooths microtopography and may influence both regression and classification, though this contribution is not quantified here. Residual sensor-side contributions, multispectral radiometric calibration and centimetre-level RTK positioning of field samples are present but minor relative to model and classification components, and were not separately propagated.

5 Conclusion

This study demonstrates that UAV multispectral imagery combined with a drone-derived CHM can support species-level AGB estimation and spatial mapping in Atlantic estuarine salt-marsh environments. Model performance was strongly conditioned by canopy architecture. For *Juncus maritimus*, the UAV-only workflow proved operationally deployable ($R^2 = 0.834$), supporting biomass monitoring and carbon stock assessment. For *Phragmites australis* and *Spartina patens*, structural and scale-related limitations point toward the need for higher-resolution 3-D structural metrics or/and larger sample sizes. The integrated pipeline – RF classification followed by species-specific regression modelling, implemented in open Python following good-practice accuracy assessment standards – provides a reproducible framework for UAV-based salt-marsh biomass monitoring, with future work prioritising improved PA classification accuracy and the exploration of 3-D structural metrics for structurally complex species. This methodology will next be applied to

the Betanzos and Ramallosa salt marshes to assess its transferability to other Atlantic estuarine systems.

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